

The CFMf topic-modeling method based on neural clustering with feature maximization: Comparison with LDA on science studies

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Abstract

Mining the content of scientific publications is increasingly used to investigate the practice of science and the evolution of research domains. Topic-models, among which LDA, have notably been shown to provide rich insights into the thematic content of disciplinary fields, their structure and evolution through time. However, improving topic modeling methods remains a major concern. Here we propose an alternative topic-modeling approach based on neural clustering and feature maximization with F1-measure (in short: CFMf). We compare the performance of this approach to LDA by applying both methods to a reference corpus of full-text philosophy of science articles ($N=16,917$). The results show significant improvements along key quantitative performance measures such as coherence, independently of the number of topics. Qualitative comparisons also show improvements in the consistency of topics and their interpretability in light of expert knowledge. We discuss these promising results and highlight upcoming research work.

Introduction

As privileged outcomes of scientific research, articles and their content provide unique insights into understanding science. Computationally mining the unstructured textual content of these articles can be an effective solution for investigating corpora of scientific texts too large for close reading. In this respect, topic-modeling can be used to reliably infer the thematic content of publications, making it possible to identify dominant research topics in specific scientific disciplines, including their evolution through time (e.g., Griffiths & Steyvers, 2004; Talley et al., 2011; Börner et al., 2021). One such well-established approach is the Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) model (Blei et al., 2003), and variants (Boyd-Graber et al., 2017). Alternative methods have recently been devised, notably some that make use of a combination of neural clustering and feature maximization with contrast (in short: CFMc) (Lamirel et al., 2020). The latter showed promising qualitative improvements compared to LDA, though thorough tests on a reference corpus of full-text philosophy of science articles ($N=16,917$) that had already been analyzed in detail by means of an LDA topic model (Malaterre & Lareau, 2022) revealed limitations in terms of top-word topic interpretability. These limitations led us to devise a novel approach still based on neural clustering with feature maximization but now relying on F1-measure (in short: CFMf). In the present research-in-progress, we describe the CFMf approach. To assess its performance in comparison to CFMc and LDA, we apply these methods to the reference corpus and compare models first quantitatively in terms of coherence (Newman et al., 2010) across several w values of number of top-words and k values of number of topics. We also assess its qualitative performance by examining the interpretability of the topics at $k = 25$ from an expert-knowledge point of view. The results show significant improvements brought about by CFMf, both in terms of performance measures and qualitative assessments.

Methods

Novel approaches to topic-modeling have been proposed that combine neural clustering for sorting documents into groups with group labeling done with feature maximization (FMax) based on contrast (Lamirel et al., 2015). These CFMc methods have shown promising results when tested on a corpus of Chinese science studies research articles (Lamirel et al., 2020). However, our preliminary experiments on the more complex dataset of philosophy of science articles —previously analyzed with LDA (Malaterre & Lareau, 2022)— highlighted three limitations: First, binary representation of words in documents, as done in CFMc, appeared too restrictive, thus encouraging the use of word frequencies; Second, contrast seemed not to be applicable in corpora whose documents did not contain clear-cut discriminative topics, hence the need to model documents as embedding several topics; And third, no quantitative comparisons with LDA had been performed.

The resulting new approach that we propose hereafter (CFMf) responds to these limitations. It still relies on neural clustering and FMax, but now uses F1-measure instead of contrast. The approach also relies on document representations as word frequency distributions (using (log of tf)-idf weighting). All documents are crisp clustered with GNG neural clustering (Fritzke, 1994), which is a winner-take-most approach based on Hebbian learning less prone to known clustering issues regarding sensitivity to outliers and to initialization (as is notably the case of methods such as *k*-means).

In a subsequent step, top words are extracted from documents in each cluster with FMax, which is a generic data comparison scheme that can be used as an alternative to usual metrics such as Chi-Square, Euclidean metric or Cosine similarity whenever dealing with sparse and high dimensional data, notably textual data. FMax provides parameter-free feature selection and feature weighting capabilities (Lamirel et al., 2015) and has proved very helpful in several data mining tasks, including graph mining (Prouteau et al., 2021). Here, features are words and FMax is based on the estimation of feature F1-measure as the harmonic mean of (1) feature recall, which focuses on word discrimination power regarding cluster data; and (2) feature predominance, which focuses on word generalization capacity regarding the same data.

To reduce noise, within each cluster, words with F1-measures below the average of all words across all clusters are then filtered out. This results in an F1-measure profile (over a reduced lexicon) for each cluster, then considered as a topic. Hence the possibility of extracting top-words based on their F1-measure ranking. To facilitate comparison with LDA, word F1-measure values are normalized for each topic.

Experimental protocol

The corpus consists of all full-text research articles from eight major philosophy of science journals that had been assembled in (Malaterre & Lareau, 2022): the *British Journal for the Philosophy of Science*, the *European Journal for Philosophy of Science*, *Erkenntnis*, *International Studies in the Philosophy of Science*, the *Journal for General Philosophy of Science*, *Philosophy of Science*, *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A* and *Synthese*. It spans from 1930 to 2017 and includes 16,917 documents. The corpus was cleaned and preprocessed in a standard way (foreign language texts had been machine-translated into English). Only nouns, verbs, adverbs and adjectives were kept following part-of-speech (POS) tagging and lemmatization (TreeTagger package (Schmid, 1994) with Penn TreeBank tag sets (Marcus et al., 1993)) and words occurring in fewer than 50 sentences in the corpus were removed. All documents were then vectorized, resulting in a term-document matrix (TDM) of word frequencies.

The TDM was then subjected to CFMc, CFMf and LDA. To quantitatively compare CFMf and CFMc, both methods were used to build models at $k = 25$. These models were then compared in terms of coherence calculated with different numbers of top-words (from $w = 5$ to 100). The objective here was to assess which method gave better results at relatively smaller w values (given that smaller sets of top-words are usually more easily interpretable than larger ones, provided they are well formed). In a subsequent step, topic-models were built both with CFMf and LDA for different numbers of topics ranging from $k = 5$ to 50 topics (by increments of 5 from 5 to 20, and by increments of 1 above 20). LDA modeling was performed following (Blei et al., 2003) and (Griffiths & Steyvers, 2004), through a Python API.

The resulting topic models were then compared using three metrics for estimating thematic consistency or coherence. First C_{PMI} , (also called C_{UCI}) following Newman et al. (2010) who had proposed to assess the quality of topics in terms of coherence as understood by human readers; this metric counts the cooccurrence of words in a sliding window and calculates, for each pair of words, its PMI (pointwise mutual information); C_{PMI} is the sum (or arithmetic means depending on implementations) of the PMI values. Second, C_{NPMI} as proposed by Aletras and Stevenson (2013) as an enhanced version of C_{PMI} using the normalized pointwise mutual information (NPMI). Third, the often used coherence measure C_V proposed by Röder et al. (2015) and implemented in the popular package Gensim in Python; C_V counts cooccurrences of a number of top-words (typically 10 to 20) in a sliding window (typically of size 110); cooccurrences are used to calculate the NPMI between top words, yielding vectors for each of them; the arithmetic mean of the cosine similarities between each top word vector and the sum of all top word vectors is then calculated. Topic names of the Malaterre & Lareau study (2022) were used to tag the LDA topics while CFMf topics were named using their top words and expert knowledge, and the topics of both models were qualitatively compared.

Results

The coherence results comparing the performance of CFMf and CFMc depending on the number of top-words (for a given number of topics $k=25$) show that CFMf models with fewer top-words clearly outperform CFMc models (Fig. 1A). This means that the F1-measure gives more coherent sets of top-words compared to contrast, at least up to $w=60$ top-words. Given an objective of topic interpretability (based on a fairly small set of ordered top-words), using the F1-measure instead of contrast provides a significant methodological improvement, which justifies the use of CFMf over CFMc in similar contexts.

When it comes to comparing CFMf with LDA, results show that CFMf largely outperforms LDA in terms of coherence measures (Fig. 1B, C, D). This is the case for all three coherence measures we tested (C_V , C_{NPMI} and C_{PMI}), and across a broad range of models with different numbers of topics (from $k=5$ to 50 topics). The coherence improvement brought about by CFMf over LDA is significant, as it ranges from about 50% for C_V up to above 200% for C_{PMI} . In all cases, coherence increases much from 5 to 20 topics, then more slowly from 20 to 40 topics, and approaches a plateau beyond 40 topics. A sweet spot therefore seems to be around 30-35 topics, depending on the objectives of the topic model. The most significant aspect of the results is the consistent quantitative outperformance of the LDA model by the CFMf model in terms of coherence.

The results of the qualitative analysis that was performed on the top-10 words of the CFMf topics show a similar type of topical coverage compared to the LDA. Remember that, for convenience, this comparison was done for $k=25$ topics since a previous LDA model had been

thoroughly examined for $k=25$ (Malaterre & Lareau, 2022). At that time, $k=25$ was chosen for pragmatic reasons, so as to have a topic-model with a relatively low number of topics. Yet, as we have just seen, higher k values show higher coherence measures, implying that $k=25$ is not optimal in this respect. Nevertheless, the 25 topics resulting from the CFMf model appeared quite easily interpretable on the basis of their top-10 words and expert-knowledge of the field. Interpretation of these topics and those of the LDA model show a reasonably good correspondence, yet the pairing is far from perfect, which shows that the topics of both models still have noticeable differences (Table 1): some topics have very similar top 10 words, while others appear to have somehow been merged or split.

Fig. 1. Performance comparisons between topic models. (A) C_V coherence of CFMf and CFMc as function of the number of top-words w (for $k = 25$ topics). (B, C, D) C_V , C_{NPMI} and C_{PMI} coherence measures of CFMf and LDA models as a function of the number of topics k (for $w = 10$ top-words).

Table 1. Comparison of the top-10 words for sample topics (CFMf and LDA).

<i>CFMf</i>	<i>Top-10 words</i>	<i>LDA topics</i>	<i>Top-10 words</i>
Knowledge (11)	belief; epistemic; justified; justification; epistemically; doxastic; reliable; testimony; proposition; agent	Knowledge (21)	belief; knowledge; epistemic; believe; know; case; evidence; reason; justification; true
Neurosciences (20)	neural; brain; processing; cognitive; input; computational; neuron; cognition; mechanism; visual	Neurosciences (13)	system; information; process; cognitive; level; mechanism; state; representation; structure; function
Causation (7)	causation; causal; cause; counterfactual; intervention; causally; woodward; probabilistic; event; counterfactuals	Causation (19)	causal; cause; event; effect; causation; condition; case; variable; time; occur
Quantum mechanics (18)	quantum; measurement; particle; mechanic; observables; spin; operator; wave; probability; bell	Explanation (16)	model; explanation; explain; account; explanatory; phenomenon; use; case; system; provide
Relativity (23)	spacetime; relativity; inertial; metric; einstein; velocity; motion; coordinate; frame; tensor	Quantum (14)	time; state; space; quantum; system; theory; particle; physical; field; point

Discussion

This first quantitative and qualitative comparison experiment shows interesting preliminary results. The CFMf method, which is an extension of CFMc that now uses the F1-measure rather than the contrast, appears more efficient than LDA in view of three performance measures as well as in terms of interpretation (at least with respect to the top-10 words of the $k = 25$ model). It would be interesting to evaluate these methods with other performance measures, notably perplexity (Wallach et al., 2009), UMass (Mimno et al., 2011), symmetric KL-Divergence (Arun et al., 2010), density (Cao et al., 2009) or Bayesian statistics (Griffiths & Steyvers, 2004). The results could also be compared to other LDA implementations (e.g. gensim package with online variational Bayes (Hoffman et al., 2010) instead of Gibbs sampling), and alternative models (e.g. Structural Topic Models (STM) (Roberts et al., 2013)). The behavior of CFMf on the documents (compared to LDA) should also be explored, to assess changes in topic probability distributions. CFMf should also be tested on other corpora: it would be interesting to investigate whether some corpora better lend themselves to one method compared to the other. While CFMf assumes that the corpus lends itself to clustering and that the identified clusters correspond to topics, it does not initially require the assumption (made in LDA) that documents are topic distributions. Furthermore, besides the number of topics, CFMf does not require any parametrization. It would also be interesting to check the robustness of results when repeating the same method on the same corpus with the same parameters. We believe CFMf to be more robust than LDA, as this method is less sensitive to random seeding and involves cooperation between prototypes that allow for thematic clusters.

Conclusion

We presented a new promising approach for building topic model based on a combination of neural clustering, feature maximization and F1 measure: CFMf. We also shared results of our comparative experiments. However, despite the clear potential of CFMf for performing large scale studies, such as science studies as shown here, there is still room for several adaptations and additional experiments. We first plan to extend our comparison with methods that are known to be efficient alternatives to LDA, like STM. We will also investigate whether LDA can be improved by using key-components of the present method, notably exploiting feature selection and FMax approaches to weigh term in LDA topics. We will further examine the effect of lexicon reduction on the two kinds of methods, while also comparing our model with topic-modeling approaches based on different corpus representations (binary, frequency,

embeddings). We also envision to investigate the feasibility to choose an optimal number k of topics, notably with a similar approach as in (Dugué et al., 2021). In the operative mode of our new model, we will examine specific strategies to combine F1-measure and contrast ranking to further optimize topic descriptions.

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References

- Aletras, N., & Stevenson, M. (2013). Evaluating topic coherence using distributional semantics. *Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Computational Semantics (IWCS 2013)–Long Papers*, 13–22.
- Arun, R., Suresh, V., Veni Madhavan, C. E., & Murthy, N. (2010). On finding the natural number of topics with latent dirichlet allocation: Some observations. *Pacific-Asia Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*, 391–402.
- Blei, D. M., Ng, A. Y., & Jordan, M. I. (2003). Latent dirichlet allocation. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 3(Jan), 993–1022.
- Börner, K., Silva, F. N., & Milojević, S. (2021). Visualizing big science projects. *Nature Reviews Physics*, 3(11), Article 11. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42254-021-00374-7>
- Boyd-Graber, J. L., Hu, Y., & Mimno, D. (2017). *Applications of topic models* (Vol. 11). now Publishers Incorporated.
- Cao, J., Xia, T., Li, J., Zhang, Y., & Tang, S. (2009). A density-based method for adaptive LDA model selection. *Neurocomputing*, 72(7–9), 1775–1781.
- Dugué, N., Lamirel, J.-C., & Chen, Y. (2021). Evaluating clustering quality using features salience: A promising approach. *Neural Computing and Applications*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00521-021-05942-7>
- Fritzke, B. (1994). A growing neural gas network learns topologies. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 7.
- Griffiths, T. L., & Steyvers, M. (2004). Finding scientific topics. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 101(suppl 1), 5228–5235. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0307752101>
- Hoffman, M., Bach, F., & Blei, D. (2010). Online learning for latent dirichlet allocation. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 23.
- Lamirel, J.-C., Chen, Y., Cuxac, P., Al Shehabi, S., Dugué, N., & Liu, Z. (2020). An overview of the history of Science of Science in China based on the use of bibliographic and citation data: A new method of analysis based on clustering with feature maximization and contrast graphs. *Scientometrics*, 125(3), 2971–2999. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-020-03503-8>
- Lamirel, J.-C., Cuxac, P., Chivukula, A. S., & Hajlaoui, K. (2015). Optimizing text classification through efficient feature selection based on quality metric. *Journal of Intelligent Information Systems*, 45(3), 379–396. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10844-014-0317-4>
- Malaterre, C., & Lareau, F. (2022). The early days of contemporary philosophy of science: Novel insights from machine translation and topic-modeling of non-parallel multilingual corpora. *Synthese*, 200(3), 242. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11229-022-03722-x>
- Marcus, M. P., Marcinkiewicz, M. A., & Santorini, B. (1993). Building a Large Annotated Corpus of English: The Penn Treebank. *Computational Linguistics*, 19(2), 313–330. <https://doi.org/10.21236/ADA273556>
- Mimno, D., Wallach, H., Talley, E., Leenders, M., & McCallum, A. (2011). Optimizing semantic coherence in topic models. *Proceedings of the 2011 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing*, 262–272.
- Newman, D., Han Lau, J., Grieser, K., & Baldwin, T. (2010). Automatic evaluation of topic coherence. *Human Language Technologies: The 2010 Annual Conference of the North American*

- Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics*, 100–108.
- Prouteau, T., Connes, V., Dugué, N., Perez, A., Lamirel, J.-C., Camelin, N., & Meignier, S. (2021). SINr: Fast Computing of Sparse Interpretable Node Representations is not a Sin! In P. H. Abreu, P. P. Rodrigues, A. Fernández, & J. Gama (Eds.), *Advances in Intelligent Data Analysis XIX* (Vol. 12695, pp. 325–337). Springer International Publishing.
- Roberts, M. E., Stewart, B. M., Tingley, D., & Airoldi, E. M. (2013). The structural topic model and applied social science. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems Workshop on Topic Models: Computation, Application, and Evaluation*, 4, 1–20.
- Röder, M., Both, A., & Hinneburg, A. (2015). Exploring the Space of Topic Coherence Measures. *Proceedings of the Eighth ACM International Conference on Web Search and Data Mining - WSDM '15*, 399–408. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2684822.2685324>
- Schmid, H. (1994). Probabilistic part-of-speech tagging using decision trees. *Proceedings of International Conference on New Methods in Language Processing*, 44–49.
- Talley, E. M., Newman, D., Mimno, D., Herr, B. W., Wallach, H. M., Burns, G. A. P. C., Leenders, A. G. M., & McCallum, A. (2011). Database of NIH grants using machine-learned categories and graphical clustering. *Nature Methods*, 8(6), 443–444. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.1619>
- Wallach, H. M., Murray, I., Salakhutdinov, R., & Mimno, D. (2009). Evaluation methods for topic models. *Proceedings of the 26th Annual International Conference on Machine Learning - ICML '09*, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1553374.1553515>